

Speculation on an Alternative Quantum Entropy

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The notion of entropy originates historically in classical physics and is intertwined with thermodynamics. Shannon's entropy: $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$, where $P(i)$ is the probability for i , however, seems to apply to any probability, but in quantum mechanics appears to be particularly linked to spatial and momentum entropy (1) i.e. $-\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln[W^*(x)W(x)]$ and $-\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \ln[a^*(p)a(p)]$ where $W(x)$ = wavefunction = $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

In this note we speculate that one may create an entropy from the real part of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\cos(px)$ as this term is associated with probability within a wavelength even though the "center of mass" of the particle may be moving uniformly at $v=x/t=\text{constant}$ and $W^*(x)W(x)=1$ or a constant. The latter implies an entropy independent of p but there is uncertainty in a free particle due to its wavelength which is experimentally manifested. We argue there is no reason to limit entropy to x or p considerations.

For a bound state, a pattern of crests and troughs of different lengths and heights may be produced and so again there is a pattern of unnormalized probability distributions with different weights. The absolute value may be taken so negative wavefunction values are not an issue. For both the free particle and the bound state two features emerge. First the shape of the distributions is linked to the curvature which in turn is associated with the kinetic energy. Thus the probability distributions which describe the quantum system are governed by kinetic energy. Secondly, a pattern of distributions, both negative and positive, ensures that $\exp(ipx)$ is perpendicular to other $\exp(ip_1 x)$ functions and $W_n(x)$ is perpendicular to other $W_{n_1}(x)$'s. In other words energy identifies the statistical state which exists throughout space and one cannot confuse the identity of one state with another. Thus they are orthogonal throughout space and probability distributions (linked to entropy) seem to enforce this. The inner product of $W^*(x)$ and $W(x)$ is like an inner product of a product probability of a state and its time reversed state.

We suggest one should be able to define a Shannon's entropy expression for both $|\cos(px)|/C_1$ from $\exp(ipx)$ over a half wavelength where C_1 is a normalization factor and $|W(x)|/C_2$ roughly over the length over which it has humps i.e. roughly the classical turning points for an oscillator for example. This entropy is not additive and does not map to classical entropy in the large n (energy level) limit. Furthermore it may not be linked to thermodynamics because it is not linked to x or p . Nevertheless, it might be used to describe uncertainty within the quantity system and equilibrium/stable scenarios which are observed in nature. For example, different $W_n(x)$ states are statistically stable states, but one may knock out the particle and it will be in an $\exp(ipx)$ state which is also stable. Furthermore, a photon may excite $W_{n_1}(x)$ to $W_{n_2}(x)$, thus this new entropy seems to be linked to stable states allowed in nature. The "price to pay", however, seems to be uncertainty in wavelength regions for a free particle and the crest/trough regions for a bound state. We also consider some properties of a similar entropy for bound states.

Free Quantum Particle

A free quantum particle is represented by two components ($\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$) or $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of momentum, but $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are each eigenfunctions of energy i.e. kinetic energy. We have argued in a previous note that the only reason one combines the two i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ is to establish a direction of motion in space such that this motion has the same probability at any x point i.e. is uniform. This is the classical mechanical scenario of a particle with constant velocity v and in quantum mechanics may be a kind of "center of mass" motion. In other words, $\cos(px)$ represents a time-independent, spatial probabilistic scenario consisting of many positive and negative probability distributions each bounded by 0. The curvature at any point yields the energy $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistically). A set of positive and negative crests/troughs is needed to establish the identity of $pp/2m$ i.e. make it orthogonal to other $\exp(ipx)$ sets if one takes the inner product of a probability and its time reversed state.

Thus $\cos(px)$ by itself represents a set of identical (except for sign) probability distributions (which may be normalized). These in turn represent uncertainty within a half wavelength which has physical consequences (i.e. two slit interference etc). One may consider uncertainty in terms of spatial density i.e. $W^*(x)W(x)$ even for the two-slit system and create a corresponding Shannon's entropy. Here we argue that a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ should have an associated entropy which is not linked to time and suggest using Shannon's entropy applied to the probability $|\cos(px)|/C1$ over a half wavelength region with $C1$ being a normalization constant i.e.

$$S_{\text{free}}(p) = - \int dx \text{ (over half a wavelength) } |\cos(px)|/C1 \ln\{ |\cos(px)|/C1 \} \quad ((1))$$

We argue that an S_{free} should exist because using a constant density, $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} * \exp(ipx) / \sqrt{L} = \text{constant}$, leads to an entropy which is the same for all p and does not show the spatial uncertainty within the different wavelengths. Furthermore this S_{free} should represent an extremum in some sense because it is the stable distribution form for a particle moving with kinetic energy $pp/2m$. The price to pay for stable quantum free kinetic energy $pp/2m$ is pockets of uncertain positions of half a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ even though the "center of mass" moves smoothly with $v=x/t$ giving the impression of each x point being the same which is not the full picture as interference experiments show.

Quantum Bound States

Classically entropies add, but $S_{\text{free}}(p)$'s do not add. Rather $\exp(ipx)$'s which are relative probabilities add to create an analogous object $W(x)$ the wavefunction = Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$. For a bound system this is real so if one has $W(x)=W(-x)$ one may use $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p$ $a(p) \cos(px)$. Thus one has two sets of uncertainties, one for x within each p half-wavelength and an uncertainty in p itself. $W(x)$ will often have a crest/trough shape, but the heights and widths will vary unlike $\cos(px)$ and there will be a rough starting and ending point linked to the classical turning points. As an example, one may consider an oscillator. If one

normalizes $|W(x)|$ within this region to obtain a $C1$, then $|W(x)|/C1$ represents a normalized probability which may be used in a Shannon's entropy expression:

$$S_{\text{bound}} = - \int dx \text{ (from one turning point to another)} |W(x)|/C1 \ln\{ |W(x)|/C1 \} \quad ((2))$$

One may note that each crest/trough region bounded by $W(x)=0$ represents a distribution on its own. One may find the entropy of each of these regions by only considering a crest or trough and computing $|W(x)|/C2$ where $C2$ is the integral of $|W(x)|$ over the crest/trough length. In such a case one may create a Shannon's entropy for each crest/trough by itself:

$$S_{\text{bound}}(\text{crest/trough } i) = \int dx \text{ (crest length)} |W(x)|/C2(i) \ln\{ |W(x)|/C2(i) \} \quad ((3))$$

A relationship between S_{bound} and the various $S(\text{bound } i)$'s is:

$$S_{\text{bound}} = -\ln(C1) - \sum \text{over } i [C2(i)/C1] \ln(C2(i)) + \sum \text{over } i C2(i)/C1 S(i) \quad ((4))$$

Thus the entropies of the various crest/troughs add with weights and two extra terms (the first two on the RHS of ((4)))

It may be asked: What is the use of these new entropy definitions? We argue that the free particle value gives an indication of the uncertainty associated with a "stable" free kinetic energy $pp/2m$ (and momentum p) with time removed completely. Usually one does not consider any entropy associated with such a particle. For the bound case, establishing "equilibrium" requires a set of distributions such that the curvature is proportional to the average kinetic energy at x if divided by $W(x)$, but at the same time the crests/troughs make this equilibrium orthogonal to other E_n equilibrium $W_n(x)$'s. Thus one has a set of probability regions (crests/troughs) each with their own entropy, but dynamics are fulfilled (i.e. conservation of energy at each x : $KE(x)+V(x) = E_n$) through curvature of the distributions and each creates a signature vector for the E_n state i.e. $W_n(x)$ which is orthogonal to other W_n1 's(x). Thus this seems to be a very different notion of entropy than that used in classical statistical mechanics. It is the uncertainty wavelength patterns which establish these goals and they are linked to a new kind of entropy we argue although for a bound state the $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ entropy is also a possible measure. We argue, however, that it does not link well with the free particle case which should have a momentum dependent entropy.

Time-Dependency

In the above we have only considered time independent solutions even for the free particle $\exp(ipx)$. In quantum mechanics there may also be time dependent $W(x,t)$'s, but these may be sometimes expanded simpl in terms of $W_n(x)$ with $a_n(t)$ factors. One may consider a probability to be in a state $W_n(x)$ at any time t and this state itself has as an entropy associated with $W_n(x)$ which is calculated above. An overall entropy as a function of x and t , however, is more complicated and not considered here.

Conclusion

In conclusion we speculate that one might be able to formulate a quantum entropy which differs from the usual $-\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*(x)W(x)\}$ or $-\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\}$. We suggest such an entropy because $\exp(ipx)$ a free particle has $W^*(x)W(x) = 1$ or $1/\text{Volume}$ for $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{V}$, but there is a wavelength which represents uncertainty in position even though there is no uncertainty in the "center of mass" motion $v=x/t = \text{constant}$ which is uniform in x regardless of p . This wavelength linked uncertainty is manifested experimentally so it seems there might be a statistical concept such as entropy associated with it. We briefly also examine the entropy of bound states.

We note that in both cases a set of probability distributions are created. For the free particle we use $|\cos(px)|$ as the distribution within half a wavelength. At the same time the pattern is repeated with crests and troughs which establish the identity of this $pp/2m = \text{energy eigenstate}$, namely that $\cos(px)$ is orthogonal to other $\cos(p_1 x)$'s. Similarly a bound state may have crests and troughs within an area roughly bounded by the classical turning points. The absolute value of these (normalized) represents a set of different probability distributions. Without the absolute value sign one has different $W_n(x)$'s being orthogonal. The shape of the distributions is governed by their curvature (proportional to average kinetic energy), but also ensures orthogonality of W_n 's. Given the various probabilities, one may construct various Shannon's entropy expressions. Thus this new proposed entropy seems to play a different role than that of the usual entropy of classical statistical mechanics.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box